

tillers do not lodge even in the water-logged fields prevalent in Bundi district. Grains are short and bold. Yield potential is 7.8 t/ha. Because of its intermediate to late duration, BK190 yields well when sown early.

BK79 (TN1/NP130//Basmati 370)

matures in 124-130 days. Panicles are compact, long, and fully exerted with a slightly brown hull at the flowering stage. It has long, slender, translucent grains. BK79 yielded 56.8% more than Basmati 370 and matured nearly 15-20 days earlier. Average yield potential is

5.3 t/ha and it has high milling and head rice recovery. It was found resistant to bacterial leaf blight and green leafhoppers.

All 3 varieties have been tested for 2-3 years in minikit trials in farmers' fields. ■

New cultivar BPT 5204 superior to Mahsuri in India

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Breeding programs at research stations in Andhra Pradesh are designed to select suitable cultivars to replace Mahsuri, a derivative of the cross Taichung 65/Mayangebos 80². Mahsuri is a weakly photoperiod-sensitive variety popular for growing during the monsoon season. Harvesting is usually in October, during the rainy season. It is a popular preference for grain quality and cooking quality. But it is medium tall and lodges even under moderate levels of nitrogen, and it lacks dormancy.

Of the crosses studied, only the pro-

Comparable performance of new cultures and Mahsuri in Andhra Pradesh.

Culture	Effective tillers (no.)	Panicle length (cm)	Height (cm)	Yield (g/plant)
BPT5656	5	20.2	69.4	12.13
BPT5657	8	20.5	72.6	15.59
BPT5204	9	18.6	68.0	15.86
BPT5322	7	20.1	71.4	15.95
Mahsuri	4	21.5	100.0	10.30
SE	0.78	0.64	1.30	1.48
CD	1.52	1.24	2.53	2.88

geny of GEB24/TNI//Mahsuri had grain quality similar to that of Mahsuri. GEB24 is a tall photoperiod-sensitive indica with commercial quality rice. From the large number of selections made from four cultures, BPT5656, BPT5657, BPT5322, and BPT5204 were promising. BPT5204 was found to be superior to Mahsuri (see table).

The harvest index of BPT5204 was 42.5%; that of Mahsuri, only 29%. BPT5204 also has a dormancy period of 1 month.

This culture has good plant type and yield, medium slender grain with the cooking quality of Mahsuri, and dormancy. It is now in minikit programs in farmers' fields. ■

Two new rice varieties

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Two short-duration, cold-tolerant, high-yielding rice strains suitable for agrocli-

matic conditions of the eastern and northeastern regions of India have been bred.

SJ-14 and SJ-15 are fine-grained strains from a cross between the widely cultivated variety Jaya and cold-

conditioned Bhutan variety Soka. The new varieties are resistant to major diseases and mature in 130 days instead of the 150 days required for traditional varieties. Average yield is 5 t/ha. ■

GENETIC EVALUATION AND UTILIZATION

Agronomic characteristics

Panicle sterility in rice variety Sita in North Bihar, India

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A new type of malformation, floret abortion, in rice variety Sita leads to panicle sterility and yield loss. Symptoms were abortion of androecium and

gynoecium and twisted lemma and palea in the florets. In some cases, florets were completely aborted (see figure). Sterility varied from 10 to 100% of the panicles and floret abortion varied from 5 to 90% of the panicle.

The malady was uniformly distributed

Twisted lemma and palea are symptoms of a new malformation — floret abortion — in North Bihar, India.

in the plot. Certain panicles in affected hills also suffered from sheath rot or bacterial leaf blight, but no correlation with panicle sterility could be traced. Diseased panicles sometimes set normal grains. Soil samples from affected and normal hills did not show any difference in nematode populations.

Symptoms were observed during 1980-81 and 1981-82 kharif, in different plots of the Jokhiat block, Purnea district, North Bihar. ■

The International Rice Research Newsletter (IRRN) invites all scientists to contribute concise summaries of significant rice research for publication. Contributions should be limited to one or two pages and no more than two short tables, figures, or photographs. Contributions are subject to editing and abridgement to meet space limitations. Authors will be identified by name, title, and research organization.

GENETIC EVALUATION AND UTILIZATION

Disease resistance

Resistance to blast and brown spot in Karnataka

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Wide distribution of blast and brown spot diseases in an epiphytotic form causes severe damage at all stages of the rice crop in many areas of Karnataka. Considerable variation in resistance to leaf blast, neck blast, and brown spot diseases occurred in 69 varieties screened during 1981 kharif. Twenty-four varieties were found resistant to leaf and neck blast disease (see table). Twenty-five varieties were found resistant to brown spot disease. Of the 69 varieties screened, only 9 showed resistance to all 3 diseases. ■

Resistance of released and unreleased varieties of rice to blast and brown spot in Karnataka

Variety	Disease score ^a		
	Leaf blast	Neck blast	Brown spot
IET3116	M	R	R
IET3305	R	M	M
IET3195	R	M	M
IET2685	R	M	M
IET2490	R	R	R
IET4699	R	R	M
IET4155	R	R	M
IET3280	M	M	R
IET3626	R	R	R
ET4094	R	R	R
IET1789	R	R	R
IET4107	R	M	R

Variety	Disease score ^a		
	Leaf blast	Neck blast	Brown spot
IET2684	R	M	R
IET5725	R	R	R
IET2444	R	R	R
IET6211	M	R	R
IET5656	M	M	M
IET5890	R	R	M
IET5854	R	R	M
IET3629	R	M	M
IET2700	R	R	R
IET2730	M	R	M
IET4555	R	R	M
IET2570	M	M	M
IET5722	R	R	M
IET4592	R	R	M
IET5704	R	M	M
IET5721	M	M	M
IET2246	R	M	M
IET5853	M	M	M
KMP32	R	R	M
KMP41	M	R	M
KMP47	R	R	M
KMP63	M	R	M
KMP64	R	R	M
KMP65	R	M	M
KMP67	R	R	M
KMP68	R	R	M
KMP70	M	R	M
KMP73	R	R	M
KMP74	R	M	M
KMP75	R	R	M
KMP42	M	R	R
83-KMP (A) 57	R	M	M
CR222-MR-10	M	M	M
CR165-18-8	M	M	M
ES-6	M	M	M
ES-18	R	M	R
ES-24	M	M	M
IR6115-1-1-1	M	M	M
Improved Madhu	M	M	M
IR8	M	M	R
S705	M	S	R
Mahsuri	M	S	M
Intan	R	R	R
Cauvery	M	S	M
Jagnath	R	S	R

Variety	Disease score ^a		
	Leaf blast	Neck blast	Brown spot
S-22	R	R	R
Madhu	R	M	M
TN1	R	M	R
Pragathi	R	M	M
MR401	M	M	R
MR362	M	R	R
MR261	R	M	R
MR343	M	M	M
Sona	R	M	R
Vani	M	R	R
ADT32	R	M	M
IR3941-8-1	R	R	M

^aR = resistant, M = moderately susceptible, S = susceptible.

Properties and concentrations of rice bunchy stunt virus

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The properties of rice bunchy stunt virus (RBSV) were determined by bioassay that involves injecting a virus source into the abdomen of *Nephotettix cincticeps*, using a capillary glass needle provided by IRR. Virus sources were prepared by homogenizing diseased materials in 0.1 M phosphate buffer solution (pH 7.0).

Infectivity of insects indicated that the dilution end point of RBSV was 10⁻⁴ of the diseased leaves and 10⁻³ of viruliferous insects. The thermal inactivation point was 60° C and longevity in vitro was 4 days at 0-4° C.